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To obtain the title of:

Chemical and Petrochemical Engineer

Prepared by:

YOUNES Afaf

**Microplastics in the marine environment, presence in water and
interaction with marine organisms**

Under the supervision of:

Dr. GARAVENTA Francesca

Dr. HOBEIKA Nelly

The jury is composed of:

Dr. AZZI Marwan

President

Dr. ASSAF Jean-Claude

Reader

Dr. CHLELA Dayane

Member

I dedicate this project to my family and my supervisors in Lebanon and Italy who supported me during the course of this project. I greatly appreciate what you did.

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ABSTRACT

Pollution of the marine environment by microplastics is a topic of increasing concern and it has received a lot of attention in recent years. This work presents a study conducted in the framework of a European project “CLAIM” (Cleaning Litter by developing & Applying Innovative Methods in European seas) in which the Lebanese University is a partner. It aims to develop innovative technologies in order to reduce the amount and impact of plastic pollution on the ecosystem-based services of the Mediterranean and Baltic Seas.

The objective of this project is to advance the knowledge on the current status of marine plastic pollution in the Gulf of Gabes area of the Mediterranean Sea, by quantifying and qualifying the microplastics in water and biota samples.

The results obtained showed a high abundance of microplastics in all marine compartments studied with an average abundance of $1.16 \text{ items/m}^3 \pm 0.83 \text{ SD}$ in the water sample. This concentration is relatively high compared to those reported in other Mediterranean regions. Dominance in number of fragments over other shapes of microplastics was reported in all sites. Polyethylene was the main plastic polymer for water samples (73% of the items analyzed are polyethylene). These data underscore that the Gulf of Gabes region is a hotspot for plastic pollution, and this calls urgently for precautionary measures.

Concerning the ingestion of microplastics by marine organisms, one blue plastic particle of 0.13 mm is found in 20 tested fishes. In addition, ecotoxicological tests were performed in order to verify whether 1-4 μm and 20-25 μm polyethylene beads are likely to trigger lethal and sub-lethal responses in marine planktonic crustaceans. The results showed that microplastics were accumulated in crustaceans, and may affect mortality specially if no future precautions were taken. These results report a better understanding of the extended threat of microplastics in the marine environment on marine species and humans.

Keywords: Microplastics, Gulf of Gabes, water pollution, crustaceans

RÉSUMÉ

La pollution du milieu marin par les microplastiques est un sujet d'actualité qui reçoit beaucoup d'attention ces dernières années. Ce travail présente une étude réalisée dans le cadre d'un projet Européen "CLAIM" (Cleaning Litter by developing & Applying Innovative Methods in European seas) dans lequel l'université Libanaise est un partenaire. Il vise à développer des technologies innovantes afin de réduire la quantité et l'impact de la pollution des microplastiques sur les services écosystémiques de la Méditerranée et de la mer Baltique.

L'objectif de ce projet est de faire progresser les connaissances sur l'état actuel de la pollution par les microplastiques au Golfe de Gabès de la Méditerranée. Ceci est réalisé en qualifiant et quantifiant les microplastiques dans des échantillons d'eau et de biote. Les résultats obtenus montrent une forte abondance des microplastiques dans tous les compartiments marins étudiés avec une abondance moyenne en nombre de $1.16 \text{ particules/m}^3 \pm 0.83 \text{ SD}$ dans l'échantillon d'eau. Cette concentration est relativement élevée par rapport à celles rapportées dans les autres régions du Méditerranée. Une dominance en nombre de fragments sur les autres types de microplastiques a été signalée. Les plastiques de nature polyéthylène étaient les plus répandus dans la colonne d'eau (73% des particules analysées sont de nature polyéthylène).

En ce qui concerne l'ingestion des microplastiques par les organismes, une particule bleue de 0,13 mm est trouvée dans 20 poissons testés. En outre, des tests écotoxicologiques ont été effectués afin de vérifier si les 1-4 et 20-25 μm billes de polyéthylène étaient susceptibles de déclencher des réponses létales et sublétales chez les crustacés planctoniques marins et les résultats montrent que les microplastiques se sont accumulés dans les crustacés et peuvent affecter la mortalité, surtout si aucune précaution future n'est envisagée. Ces résultats rapportent une compréhension plus profonde de l'ampleur de la menace des microplastiques présents dans l'environnement marin sur les espèces marines et sur l'homme même.

Mot-Clé : Microplastiques, Golfe de Gabès, pollution marine, crustacés planctoniques marins

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND SYMBOLS

CLAIM	Cleaning Litter by developing and Applying Innovative Methods in European seas
MPs	Microplastics
PE	Polyethylene
PP	Polypropylene
PS	Polystyrene
PA	Polyamide
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
PETE	Polyethylene Terephthalate
LDPE	Low-Density Polyethylene
HDPE	High-Density Polyethylene
EVA	Ethylene-Vinyl Acetate
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
ZnO	Zinc Oxide
H ₂ O	Pure Water
H ₂ O ₂	Hydrogen Peroxide
•OH	Hydroxyl Radical
BPA	Bisphenol A
<i>PE</i>	<i>Pagellus Erythrinus</i>
<i>SS</i>	<i>Scomber Scombrus</i>
ATR	Attenuated Total Reflectance
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infra Red Spectroscopy
AOP	Advanced Oxidation Process
BDPs	Biodegradable Plastics
PBT	Persistent, Bioaccumulative, and Toxic substances
UV	Ultraviolet

UNEP	United Nations Environment Program
FSW	Filtred Sea Water
GPS	Global Positioning System
SD	Standard Deviation
e ⁻	Electron
h ⁺	Hole
MT	Millions Tons
MTPY	Million Tons Per Year
μm	Micrometer
mm	Millimeters

INTRODUCTION

Plastic pollution is an emerging and growing threat across world oceans and has been the subject of an increasing number of studies and surveys since 2000. Global plastics production has consistently increased over recent years and the amount of plastic produced in the world today is 170 times greater than it was 60 years ago, 335 million tons per year (MTPY) to be exact [1]. Due to its durability, low cost, and widespread application, plastic is a material of vast benefits to society. Therefore, plastics production is likely to increase even further.

Once in the environment, plastics tend to break down into smaller debris called microplastics (MPs), and they can be defined as ubiquitous plastic particles smaller than five millimeters (5 mm) in size, of various shapes, color and polymer composition [2]. The biggest part of these MPs is found in the seas and oceans. In 2010, the amount of plastic waste reaching the oceans was estimated between 4 to 12 MTPY, and without proper management measures, the predictions indicate an increase by an order of magnitude by 2025 [3]. The figure below shows the distribution of plastic litter hotspots in the oceans.

Figure 1. Mapping of plastic litter hotspots in global oceans. Source: ESA (2018)

With a size spectrum and buoyancy comparable to most planktonic organisms, MPs are likely to be ingested by higher trophic level organisms (fish, bivalves) and could accumulate along the food chain [4][5].

In the Mediterranean Sea, the MPs analyses are increasing on the last year but a significant data gap can be identified especially for what concerns South Mediterranean countries. To fill this gap, and since Tunisia is a partner in CLAIM project, this study aims to evaluate, for the first time, the MPs pollution of the Tunisian coast (Gulf of Gabes).

The main goals of the present study are:

- 1) Monitoring and assessing the MPs abundance in two environmental compartments (sea surface water and marine biota) by determining MPs abundance, types, sizes, and polymer composition.
- 2) Studying the effects of MPs on marine crustaceans represented by the brine shrimps *Artemia*.

This manuscript consists of three chapters:

The **first chapter** is a literature review that exposes the origin and the importance of plastics, the problems caused by its excessive use, as well as the biodegradable alternatives of plastic. The definition of MPs, their sources, categories and distribution in the aquatic environment is also presented. Moreover, the threats of MPs to the environment and their treatment processes are studied. Finally, results from previous studies on the MPs abundance in the Mediterranean are listed in order to compare our results with previous ones.

The **second chapter** presents the sampling sites and details the method of MPs sampling from surface sea water. In addition, it explains the experimental procedure starting from sample handling, MPs separation from sea water and biota samples, and finally the characterization using Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). Moreover, ecotoxicological tests are performed in order to study the effects of two different sizes of polyethylene (PE) MPs on the marine organisms represented by the nauplii of the brine shrimp *Artemia* sp., which is considered as a model extremophile organism offering a unique suite of adaptations.

The **third chapter** is devoted to results and discussion. It focuses on the distribution of MPs in water and biota samples, according to their shape, size and polymeric nature. These results allow better understanding of the situation of the Gulf of Gabes compared to other Mediterranean countries. The

effects of PE MPs on nauplii of the brine shrimp *Artemia* sp. in terms of mortality and immobilization are also presented.

Finally, a conclusion will be made on all the performed work by opening the prospects for future research.

CHAPTER I - LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter concerns the origin of plastics, the advantages and disadvantages of using it and its degradation to MPs. In addition, it covers the types, categories, sources, distribution and threat of MPs to the aquatic environment. Moreover, it presents the biodegradable alternatives to plastics as well as the possible treatment technologies focusing on the photocatalytic device.

I.1 Origin of plastics

Although the very first plastics, made from natural plastic materials such as rubber, chewing gum and shellac were already made and used as early as 1600 BC and Middle Ages, the invention of modern, synthetic plastic only started in the 1800s.

Parkesine (nitrocellulose) is considered the first man-made plastic. The plastic material was patented by Alexander Parkes in England in 1856 and it was unveiled in the 1862. Parkesine was made from natural cellulose (in the form of cotton or wood pulp) treated with nitric acid as a solvent. The output of the process, commonly known as cellulose nitrate, could be dissolved in alcohol and hardened into a transparent and elastic material that could be molded when heated. By incorporating pigments into the product, it could be made to resemble ivory.

Table 1. Important dates in the history of plastic

1862	Alexander Parks invents and patents the first man-made plastic material, Parkesine
1869	John Wesly Hyatt develops the first synthetic polymer when trying to find an ivory substitute
1905	Leo Baekeland creates the first fully synthetic thermoset, Bakelite, the first fully synthetic plastic compound that was used on a large scale
1920-1950	Many new kinds of plastic, such as Polystyrene (PS), Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC), and polyethylene (PE) are discovered and mass produced
1954	Giulio Natta discovers Polypropylene (PP)

The production and use of plastic materials have increased steadily since the start of the industrial manufacturing in the 1950s. Plastic materials have become indispensable for numerous applications in our everyday lives and are important in many sectors including the transportation, electronics, construction, packaging, agriculture, food safety, health, hygiene and textile industries.

Figure 2. shows the increase in plastic demand from 2015 to 2016 for each polymer type. As we can see, the demand for PP and PE is the highest and this is due to their easy processability and low price in

Figure 2. Plastic demand by type of resin (measured in millions tons)

combination with their good chemical and physical properties, which makes them the most popular resins and often the best choice for a multitude of plastic applications.

It is very difficult to realise how important plastics have become to our everyday lives. We always seem to know these materials, and we tend to take it for granted that they occur everyday and all around us, for example in our clothing, the pen that we write with, the chair that we sit on or the wrapping of the food that we eat.

It is sometimes hard to believe that plastics have only been commonly available for about the last one hundred years. Yet in this time, the impact that they have made upon the quality of our lives and on the products that we have access to has been enormous.

I.2 What are plastics and how they are made?

The word “plastic” comes from the Greek word “plastikos” meaning “to grow” and it can be defined as a group of materials, either synthetic or naturally occurring that may be shaped when soft and then

hardened to retain the given shape. Plastics are polymers, and polymer is a large molecule made of repeating smaller units called monomers.

These plastics can be derived from coal, natural gas, and, of course, crude oil. Crude oil is a complex mixture of thousands of compounds and needs to be processed before it can be used. Today, 4% of the world crude oil is used to make plastics.

The production of plastics begins with **drilling and extraction** of oil from the reserves, after extraction, the oil is transported by either pipelines or tanker to the refinery.

In the **refinery**, a distillation column is used to separate the heavy crude oil into groups of lighter component, called fractions. Each fraction is a mixture of hydrocarbon chains which differ in term of the size, weight and boiling temperature.

Figure 3. Crude oil to plastic production process

One of these fractions, naphtha, is sent to plastics processing plant where it is heated by process called **steam cracking** which breaks it down further into a number of products: ethylene, propylene, benzene and many others. All these products are processed further in petrochemical plants using **polymerization** in order to produce PE, PP and PS in the form of pellets or granules. These plastic granules, are the raw material used in the **manufacture of plastic products** such as drink bottles, caps and food containers. The basic polymer is always incorporated with different “additives”. Additives are

chemical compounds added to improve the performance, functionality and ageing properties of the polymer. These additives can be mainly divided into the following 3 categories [6]:

1. Functional additives (stabilizers, antistatic agents, flame retardants, plasticizers, lubricants, slip agents, foaming agents, biocides)
2. Fillers: natural substances used to increase the modulus and lower the cost of the material (mica, talc, clay, calcium carbonate)
3. Reinforcements: used to reinforce or increase the mechanical properties of a polymer composite (glass fibers, carbon fibers)

The most commonly used additives are listed in table 2. Each of them plays a distinct role in delivering/enhancing the final functional properties of a plastic product.

Table 2. Use and application for most common additives

Additive compounds	Function
Plasticizers	Used for improving the flexibility, durability and stretch ability of polymeric films
Antioxidants	Delay the overall oxidative degradation of plastics if/when exposed to ultraviolet (UV) light
Heat stabilizers	Prevent thermal degradation of polymers when exposed to elevated temperatures
Slip agents	Reduce the surface coefficient of friction of a polymer

Most plastics contain 0-50% of additives and the average content is 20% by weight of the polymer. The additives are not covalently bonded to the polymer, so they can leach out of the plastics as they degrade and enter into the marine environment [7].

I.3 Advantages and disadvantages of using plastic products

Plastics may seem the perfect material for any kind of market. First of all, it is inexpensive, durable and very resistant. Also, plastic is easy to work and shape, making it suitable for a great variety of usages. These characteristics made plastic the most used material in industry. Plastics are important in our society providing a range of benefits for human health and the environment [8]. For example:

- Plastic water supply systems and storage containers/tanks can provide clean water.
- Low-density plastic materials, used as replacements for metals or ceramics in cars and aircraft, save fuel and decrease emissions.
- Plastic protective clothing and safety equipment (e.g. fire proof materials, helmets, airbags) prevent injuries.
- Plastic products for medical applications contribute to improved health (e.g. blood pouches, disposable syringes)

In Europe, the use of plastics is mostly dominated by packaging (38%), followed by building and construction (21%), automotive (7%), electrical and electronic (6%), and other sectors (28%), such as medical and leisure [9]. Table 3 summarize the most common synthetic polymers and their uses.

Table 3. Most common synthetic polymers and their uses

Polymer	Polymer structure	Resin identification code	Uses
Polyethylene terephthalate (PETE)		Soft drink bottles, solar cells, food packaging (microwavable meals)	
High density polyethylene (HDPE)		Plastic chairs and tables, vehicle fuel tanks, detergent bottles	
Polyvinyl chloride (PVC)		Raincoats, automobile seat covers, electricity pipes	
Low-density polyethylene (LDPE)		Plastic bags, computer hardware covers, dispensing bottles	
Polypropylene (PP)		Bottle caps, fishing nets, plastic cups	
Polystyrene (PS)		Laboratory ware such as Petri dishes, CD case, trays	

Despite the appealing characteristics of this material, the downsides connected to the usage of plastics are many and the greatest environmental concern is its disposal. Large volumes of plastic wastes are generated, mainly due to the short life span of many plastic products (it is estimated that approximately 40% of plastic products have a service life of less than 1 month) [10]. This large waste creates serious environmental and management problems. In fact, plastic is never biodegradable and as such its end-of-life disposal is particularly delicate. Plastic can go through photo-degradation, meaning that in a time span of 450 to 1000 years, it can disappear by being exposed to the sun. When plastics are under water, this process will take even longer because sunlight has difficulty penetrating. Figure 4 displays the degradation rate of everyday plastic items found in the marine environment.

Figure 4. Estimated number of years for selected items to biodegrade in a marine environment

Furthermore, there is a wide range of types of plastic and not all of them can be recycled, and even when they can be recycled, the process is complicated, expensive and it decreases its quality over time. According to UNEP (United Nations Environment Program), between 20% and 40% of the world’s plastic waste are thrown in landfills where they occupy valuable space and pollute the environment. In figure 5, the industries that produce the largest amounts of plastic waste are shown. Packaging, for example, has a very short “in use” lifetime (typically around 6 months or less). This is in contrast to building and construction sectors, where plastic use has a mean lifetime of 35 years [11]. The packaging

sector is therefore the dominant generator of plastic waste, responsible for almost half of the global total.

Figure 5. Global plastic waste generation by industrial sector, measured in tonnes per year

I.4 Biodegradable alternatives to plastic

Most synthesized polymers are not biodegradable under normal environmental conditions. Degradation will occur under favorable conditions, such as higher temperatures, physical abrasion and exposure to UV radiation, with the rate dependent on the type of polymer and presence of stabilizing compounds, but this leads simply to weakening and fragmentation.

New polymers meant to either biodegrade or to last longer would reduce waste. Biodegradable plastics (BDPs) refer to polymeric materials that can break down in the environment into naturally occurring components, not just smaller pieces of themselves. BDPs could replace many applications for petroleum derived plastics, however cost and performance remain problematic. (The cost of BDP polymers fall in the range of 2–5 €/Kg compared with approximately 1.2 €/Kg for major petrochemical polymers) [12].

Types of biodegradable plastics include: starch-based plastics, cellulose-based plastics and protein-based plastics.

Starch-based plastics are more cost competitive than alternative bioplastics. Starch is a polysaccharide, consisting of linked glucose molecules, and is used as an energy store in plants. It is one of the most important forms of carbohydrate in the human diet. Common sources of starch include rice, maize, wheat and potatoes.

Figure 6. Starch molecule structure

In fact, starch-based bioplastics are widely employed in the medical industry because of their biocompatibility, low toxicity, degradation properties and mechanical properties.

There are significant downsides. Although the bioplastic items might be biodegradable, some items (especially plastic bags) might release metals during the decomposition process. The polyethylene created through the manufacturing cycle using natural items may contain high levels of manganese, which can stop breaking down when you begin the composting process for these items. In addition, bioplastics will not solve ocean pollution problems because bioplastics cannot decompose in ocean water because it is too cold of an environment for the material and thus it will either float on the surface like a conventional product or create MPs that are harmful to marine life.

I.5 Microplastics definition and categories

When plastics enter the environment, and due to mismanagement and improper disposal, they are subjected to physical, chemical and biological degradation processes that will transform them into smaller fragments classified as "microplastics" [13].

The degradation occurs through exposure to UV radiation from the sun, abrasion or by the action of washing synthetic nylon or polyester clothing which can release thousands of plastic fibers into wastewater [14].

The term “microplastics” was first used in 2004 to describe tiny fragments of plastic in the water column and in sediments [15]. Nowadays, in general context, MPs is used as collective term to describe a heterogeneous mixture of particles up to 5 mm in size, including particles of various shapes from completely spherical to elongated fibers. This study deals with micro sized plastics and their presence in the marine environment.

MPs are themselves divided into two categories, **primary MPs** and **secondary MPs**.

The distinction between primary and secondary MPs is based on whether the particles were originally engineered to be that size (primary) or whether they have resulted from the breakdown of larger items (secondary) [16]. Examples of primary MPs include resins pellets (used within the plastics industry as the raw material), industrial abrasives and abrasives in personal care products such as toothpaste. Examples of secondary MPs include fibers from synthetic textiles, dust from vehicles tires and fragments from the wide variety of plastic object in everyday use, including fishing nets, containers and packaging.

This distinction is useful since it can help to indicate potential sources and identify mitigation measures to reduce their input to the environment.

I.6 Sources of microplastics

Sources of marine litter are traditionally classified as either land-based or sea-based, depending on where the litter enters the water. They can enter directly into the marine environment by commercial and recreational **fishing** which rejects monofilm lines plastic and nylon nets. These types of plastics generally have neutral buoyancy and can reach the bottom. **Ships** also contribute significantly to marine litter by dumping plastic packaging materials, as well as marine industries (such as oil rigs and power generating boats). Additionally, **coastal tourism** and coastal landfills play an important role as a source of MPs which through lack of management and maintenance, can bring waste into the marine environment.

Another notable source of plastic debris is the **environmental action**. As plastic waste and debris floats around the ocean, they are exposed to the elements of harsh solar radiation and constant abrasion from

the action of wind and water waves. Over time, these elements break down the plastics into smaller chunks of debris and the cycle continues on and on until the remaining debris become microscopic [.

While environmental action is the most common way that MPs are formed, the other relevant means comes from **intentional human production of small beaded plastics**. These have found use in the skin care and hygiene industry where small plastic microbeads are added to products such as shower gels and facial scrubs to increase their abrasive qualities and ensure that they provide proper exfoliation and cleaning.

Other source of MPs come in the shape of microfibers which unlike beads, are longer. They are product of **human clothing** and when one washes plastic clothing, it sheds MP fibers into the water, approximately 1900 fibers can be released in the water in a single wash [17].

Although, the major sources of MPs are land based, in general, it is extremely difficult to confidently identify and point out the ultimate sources of MPs because of their fragment nature, small size, varying sources and their ability to travel long distances before being deposited onto shorelines or settling on the bottom of the sea or ocean.

I.7 Distribution of microplastics in the aquatic environment

Plastics do not always behave the same way, and that is why it is hard to know their final destination in the marine environment. Polymers that have a lower density than seawater will tend to float in the water column while those that are denser will sink to the bottom.

Table 4. Specific densities of different polymer types commonly encountered in marine environment

Abbreviation	Polymer	Density (g cm ⁻³) *	Buoyancy
PS	Polystyrene	0.01 – 1.06	Positive (↑)
PP	Polypropylene	0.85 – 0.92	Positive (↑)
LDPE	Low-density polyethylene	0.89 – 0.93	Positive (↑)
EVA	Ethylene vinyl acetate	0.93 - 0.95	Positive (↑)
HDPE	High-density polyethylene	0.94 – 0.98	Positive (↑)
Seawater		1.025	
PA	Polyamide	1.12 – 1.15	Negative (↓)
PA 6,6	Nylon 6,6	1.13 – 1.15	Negative (↓)
PMMA	Poly methyl methacrylate	1.16 – 1.20	Negative (↓)
PC	Polycarbonate	1.20 – 1.22	Negative (↓)
PU	Polyurethane	1.20 – 1.26	Negative (↓)
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate	1.38 – 1.41	Negative (↓)
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride	1.38 – 1.41	Negative (↓)

Table 4 and figure 7 illustrate which polymers tend to float and which tend to sink in the ocean. The density of sea water ranges from about 1.02 to 1.03 g.cm⁻³ depending on the salinity, depth and temperature variations [18]. As seen in the table, PS, PP and PE (HD and LD) are floating on water surface which suggest that they will be the most abundant MPs types detected on the sea water surface.

Figure 7. Schematic of which synthetic polymers tend to float and which tend to sink in the ocean

However, several variables, that are more or less studied, can modify the density and therefore, even low density plastics can reach the seabed [19,20]. MPs of similar types were found in the water column and sediments [21,22]. These variables include:

- Change of the buoyance by accumulation of organism on immersed surface (biofouling)
- Fragmentation rate (size distribution)
- Conditions of the marine environment (circulation of water, tides, wind)
- Degradation rate (persistence)
- Influence of hot-spots and proximity to populated areas.

I.8 Threat of microplastics to the aquatic environment

Plastics present clear risks for the environment, leading to the death of countless fishes and birds. The color of the MPs can potentially contribute to the likelihood of ingestion, because of the similarity

between prey [23]. These MPs can reach the highest levels of a marine food web, such as sea turtles, fulmar, and sea lions by direct ingestion or by trophic transfer through fish that have consumed MPs [24]. The ingestion of MPs can influence marine animals in different ways (figure 7). It can affect the immune system, both chemically (caused by the substances that MPs may contain, absorb or release, which may be toxic) or physically by blocking the digestive organs and preventing the animals from feeding.

Figure 8. Effects of microplastics on marine fish [25]

One example on the effect of MPs, in oysters, PS cause a decrease in the number of oocytes, the diameter and speed of sperm which affect their reproduction [26], they can also cause ulcers, signs of liver stress and obstructions in the digestive tract, which can cause satiety, starvation or even death of fish [27].

Additives used in the production of plastics, such as bisphenol A (BPA), accumulate in aquatic species through the process of bioaccumulation, causing disruption of the endocrine system.

MPs have the capacity to absorb lubricating oils, heavy metals and toxins present in water and during ingestion in aquatic organisms can be desorbed and accumulated in adipose tissue [28].

It's not only animal consumption of plastic and ocean well-being that is causing grave concern. Plastic is also increasingly contributing to climate change. A 2019 report by the Tear Fund states that global plastic production emits 400 MT of greenhouse gases each year. Moreover, a study from the University

of Hawaii found that plastic is known to release a variety of harmful chemicals as it breaks up. When exposed to solar radiation, the most commonly used plastics produce two greenhouse gases, methane and ethylene. Methane alone is roughly 30 times more potent a heat-trapping gas than carbon dioxide [29].

I.9 Are microplastics affecting our health?

Currently there is no clear evidence whether MPs have a serious effect on humans as it does on marine organisms, as the level of MPs ingested is not at sufficient concentrations to cause the same issues as it does in marine animals. In humans the risk of MPs ingestion is reduced by the removal of the gastrointestinal tract in most species of seafood consumed. However, most species of bivalves and several species of small fish are consumed whole, which may lead to MPs exposure. A worst case estimate of exposure to MPs after consumption of a portion of mussels (225 g) would lead to ingestion of 7 micrograms (μg) of plastics.

Chemically speaking, the plastics themselves are generally inert and have minimal effect on human health. However, additives and sorbed contaminants, such as persistent, bioaccumulative, and toxic substances (PBTs) have the potential to negatively affect human health [30]. PVC for example, contains plasticizers such as phthalates and BPA. BPA is one of the best studied chemicals found in plastic and it is usually found in plastic packaging or food storage containers. BPA doesn't remain in the plastic but leaches out and migrates into adjacent substances like water, food or even saliva. Some evidence has shown that BPA can interfere with reproductive hormones, especially in women causing human health problems such as prostate cancer, type-2 diabetes, obesity and cardiovascular disease.

In addition, phthalates, a chemical used to make plastic flexible, have shown to increase the growth of breast cancer cells. However, this research was carried out in a petri dish, so the results can't be generalized to humans [31].

Moreover, PBTs are hydrophobic chemicals which have a long life in the environment as they are resistant to environmental degradation and may persist for several years. Their hydrophobicity drives the partitioning to MPs and organic particles. As plastics also have hydrophobic properties, MPs act as a sink for these pollutants present in aquatic environments. A common concern about PBTs is the possibility of trophic transfer and bioaccumulation. PBTs build up in the tissues of organisms and accumulate up the food chain, leading to increased body burdens in higher trophic levels. However, in

contrast to PBTs, most MPs ingested will not translocate into the tissues of their hosts, and thus would not be retained and concentrated at subsequent higher trophic levels.

Micro-particles including MPs have shown to pass from the intestines into the blood and potentially into other organs [32]. The figure below explains how the body interact with the plastic particles according to their size. All MPs sizes will affect our body with the smaller ones being the most harmful.

Figure 9. An example on how consumed plastic particles could interact with our body [33]

I.10 Microplastics treatment technologies

The last decades have shown a reevaluation of the environmental pollution issue. Reducing the amount of pollutants in water remains the main goal of the most of nations in order to reduce the diseases caused by water pollution. Stop throwing the plastic garbage away, buy environment-safe cleaning products and reduce the amount of insecticides and pesticides used in agriculture are the main ideas that came to the mind to minimize the water pollution. However, since wastewater from industries and sewage are the main sources that affect and can significantly increase the rate of water pollution, and since the MPs are not readily visible to the naked eye, the development of effective and affordable technologies to treat these pollutants is therefore the effective way to reduce the rate of pollution.

In the past, several physical techniques like coagulation, flocculation, sand filtration, and chemical methods like photosensitized oxidation, adsorption [34], have been used to reduce the toxic effluents from waste water [35]. However, the main drawback of these techniques is formation of secondary waste product which can not be treated again and dumped as such [36].

Therefore, attention has been focused on the oxidation of organic compounds to harmless products such as carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water (H₂O) using the **Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOP)**. AOPs are chemical – physical systems which have been developed as new technologies for water purification. AOPs make use of different types of energy such as ultrasounds, UV light and ionizing radiation to generate a number of reactive species that attack toxic pollutants in wastewaters. Among the reactive species produced by the AOPs, hydroxyl radical (\bullet OH) plays a major role, it reacts unselectively once formed and contaminants will be quickly and efficiently fragmented and converted into CO₂ and H₂O. In fact, through these processes, the polluting molecules can be destroyed in an effective and sustainable way.

The main AOP is the **photocatalysis** which use the solar power and a semiconductor-based photocatalyst to remove the organic contaminants. Figure 10 explains the principle of the photocatalytic device

Figure 10. Mechanism of the photocatalytic reaction

When the photocatalyst is photo-induced by solar light with photonic energy ($h\nu$) equal to or greater than the excitation energy, the electron of the valence band (VB) becomes excited to the conduction band (CB) of the catalyst therefore creating the negative-electron (e^-) and positive-hole (h^+). This stage is referred as the semiconductor's photo-excitation state. The h^+ reacts with water and hydroxide ions to produce hydroxyl radicals. Then, the hydroxyl radicals will attack the pollutants adsorbed on

the surface of the photocatalyst to produce intermediate compounds, these intermediates will be then converted to green compounds such as CO₂, H₂O and mineral acids. The team of CLAIM scientists relied on the photocatalysis principal to develop a small scale photocatalytic nanocoating device. This device will speed up UV-fueled degradation and breaking down of MPs into harmless elements. Other innovative technologies developed by CLAIM include a small-scale thermal treatment device (pyrolizer) that will be used for energy recovery from collected litter on board ships and ports.

Additionally, a method to measure microlitter on board ships will operate in the Baltic, West & East Mediterranean mounted with an automated seawater sampling device and passive flow-through filtering system.

Other recommendations to reduce the loss of MPs include the use of disc filter which attracts MPs and prevent them from reaching the sea and ocean and onsite treatment of MPs

I.11 The Mediterranean: one example of the impact of marine microplastics

The Mediterranean Sea has been described as one of the areas most affected by marine litter in the world. Being the largest and deepest enclosed Sea on earth, one of the busiest navigation crossroads and top touristic destinations in the world, surrounded by a heavily populated and industrialized coastline, it is not surprising that in this basin, the impacts of human activities are proportionally stronger than in any other sea. Its water has a 90-year renewable period and plastics persist for periods in excess of 100 years.

The Mediterranean Sea accounts for 7% of the world's MP waste, yet 1% of its water. And in this area, a high concentration of floating debris has been reported with the majority of objects counted (from 60 to 70%) in the form of plastic pieces [37].

In 2016 a study was carried out in Turkey for the detection of MPs in fish and in seawater. In 28 different species, 58% of the total fish had an average of 2.36, and 41% had an average of 1.80 particles per fish. The quantity of MPs in the water samples collected at 18 locations on the coast Mediterranean Turkey was between 16,339 and 520,213 MPs per km² with a dominance of blue plastics [38].

In the same period, in 2016, another study was done in Palestine in order to detect MPs in seawater; samples were taken at 17 locations on the Mediterranean coast of Palestine. MPs were found in all samples with an average of 1,518,340 particles/km² with a dominance of clear colors such as white and transparent plastics [39].

There is no significant data about the presence, quantification and qualification of MPs in the Gulf of Gabes area, that's why in this study, we will cover this area of the Mediterranean Sea.

CHAPTER II - MATERIALS AND METHODS

This chapter is divided into two parts, the first part presents the sampling sites, details the method of MPs sampling, sample handling and characterization for both water and fish samples. In the second part, ecotoxicological tests are performed in order to study the effects of MPs on the marine organisms.

II.1 Zone of study and sampling sites

In this project, studies focus on assessing the MPs abundance in the Gulf of Gabes area. It is a gulf on Tunisia's east coast in the Mediterranean Sea. The gulf is 100 km long and 100 km wide and is bounded by the Kerkennah Islands on the northeast and by Jerba Island on the southeast and at the head of the gulf is the city of Gabès (Ghannouche) where the tides have a large range of up to 2.1 m at spring tides.

Figure 11. Location of the Gulf of Gabes[40].

The MPs analysis are done on water samples taken from 6 stations along the gulf. The location of those stations is illustrated in figure 12 and table 5. The stations selected are located near ports and rivers which are considered as main sources point for the entry of MPs to the sea.

Figure 12. Map showing the locations of the sampling stations

Table 5. Station number, position (latitude and longitude) and sampling date of water samples

Sample ID	Station 4	Station 5	Station 7	Station 8	Station 16	Station 17
Start time	13h55	14h37	11h24	12h06	09h25	09h59
Start latitude	N34°00'386"	N 34°00'494"	N33°55'507"	N33°56'691"	N 33°46'789"	N 33°47'769"
Start longitude	E010°03'449"	E010°05'959"	E010°07'044"	E010°08'33"	E 010°15'701"	E 010°16'824"
Stop time	14h10	14h55	11h39	12h21	09h40	10h14
Stop latitude	N34°00'588"	N 34°00'397"	N33°56'248"	N33°57'185"	N 33°47'354"	N 33°48'284"
Stop longitude	E010°04'353"	E010°06'858"	E010°07'863"	E010°09'148"	E 010°16'384"	E 010°17'442"
Volume filtered (m3)	240	231	301	254	246	215

The Gulf of Gabes is the only part of the Mediterranean with a substantial tidal range causing the uncovering of extensive sandbanks at low water. It is also considered highly productive, contributing approximately 40% of the national fish production in Tunisia [41]. Both Gabes and Sfax are major ports on the gulf, supporting sponge and tuna fisheries, with Gabes being the economic and administrative center.

II.2 Samples collection

II.2.1 Sea water sampling procedure

MPs sampling by manta net is a widely used method for the sampling of MPs on the sea surface, but to date there has been no unified methodology. In this study, we report the procedure followed to sample the MPs using a manta net.

In April 2019, water samples were collected using a 330 μm mesh size towed manta net having the dimension of the mouth of 25x65 cm.

Figure 13. Schematic drawing of the manta net used for microplastics sampling

The sampling procedure is explained below [42]:

1. Deploy the net out of the wake zone (approximately 3-4 m distance from the boat) in order to prevent collecting water affected by turbulence inside the wake zone (figure 14, A)
2. Write down the initial GPS coordinates and initial time in the data sheet
3. Start to move in one straight direction for approximately 15 minutes and begin the time measurement

4. After 15 minutes, stop the boat and write down final GPS coordinates, the length of the route (the most correct way is to calculate the length from the GPS coordinates) and the average boat speed into the data sheet provided and lift the manta net out of the water
5. Rinse the manta net thoroughly from the outside of the net with seawater using water from the boat water reservoir. Rinse in the direction from the manta mouth to the cod end in order to concentrate all particles adhered to the net into the cod end (figure 14,B)
6. Safely remove the cod end and the materials retained is carefully transferred into new plastic bottles. Rinse the cod end thoroughly from the outside and pour the rest of the sample through the sieve. Repeat this step until there are no longer any particles inside the cod end (figure 14,C)
7. Close the bottle, label the lid and outside of the jar with the sample name and date with waterproof marker
8. Unless required, remove large pieces (algae, wood, organisms such as jellyfish) from the sample. Rinse them thoroughly with water from a wash bottle to ensure that all plastic is retained.

Figure 14. Sea water sampling steps: (A) manta net is deployed in water, (B) the net is recovered and washed, (C) the cod end is removed

Attention should be given to the method used to measure the filtered and the analyzed volume. The **filtered volume** is the total volume from which we collected the MPs and it is calculated by multiplying the area of the mouth of the net by the distance covered during the tow. The later is obtained from the GPS data. This volume is the correct one to be used to calculate the MPs abundance. In the other hand,

the **analyzed volume** is the water volume that we added in the laboratory to the Petri dish for MPs observation under the microscope.

II.2.2 Fish samples collection

The fish samples studied were not sampled directly from the sea, they were purchased in May 2019 from the market of Gabes. The samples consist of 20 commercially available fishes: 10 *Pagellus erythrinus* (*PE*) and 10 *Scomber scombrus* (*SS*) specimens.

PE is a popular food fish in Mediterranean countries, with delicate white flesh. It has a slim, oval body, with a smallish mouth and scales covering its face (figure 15, A). It is silver in color with a pink tinge, particularly on its back. A typical specimen measures 10–30 cm.

SS are found in the Mediterranean Sea, the Black Sea, and the northern Atlantic Ocean. It has an elongate body with a long, pointed snout (figure 15, B). *SS* is a highly commercial species and it is sought after for its meat, which is strong in flavor and high in oil content and omega-3 fatty acids among other nutrients. Nearly 1 million tonnes of this species are caught each year globally, and it is sold fresh, frozen, smoked, or canned.

Figure 15. The fish samples studied (A: *Pagellus erythrinus* and B: *Scomber scombrus*)

Table 6. summarize the details of both fish samples. The total and standard length (the standard length is defined as the total length without the caudal fin) are measured in centimeters (cm). The total weight and the weight without the guts are recorded in grams (g).

Table 6. Dimensions and weight of the biota samples

PE sample ID	PE1	PE2	PE3	PE4	PE5	PE6	PE7	PE8	PE9	PE10
Total length	19.2	19.9	18.9	19.9	18.6	18.9	19.7	19.8	19.1	19.4
Standard length	14.9	15.6	14.6	15.8	15.7	15.2	15.8	15.9	14.9	15.3
Total weight	79.3	104.88	81.16	92.55	78.72	78.92	95.67	97.99	84.73	86.18
Weight without the guts	75.72	93.39	78.83	86.91	74.7	77.92	91.47	93.35	79.41	82.45
SS sample ID	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS4	SS5	SS6	SS7	SS8	SS9	SS10
Total length	18.3	18.3	18.9	18.4	18.8	18.9	19.7	18.9	19.4	18.6
Standard length	16.9	17.9	17.8	16.2	16.9	16.4	17.2	16.6	16.7	16.4
Total weight	66.23	66.3	44.75	50.38	59.4	56.21	60.86	57.3	55.91	48.12
Weight without the guts	60.44	59.16	40.78	46.47	54.63	51.84	55.88	51.36	51.4	44.01

II.3 Samples laboratorial analysis

II.3.1 Analysis of sea water samples

Analysis of water samples starts by the separation of all potential MP items, classification according to physical properties (II.3.1.1) and chemical properties (II.3.1.2).

II.3.1.1 Microplastics separation and physical identification

In order to isolate the MP particles from sea water samples, the below procedure is followed:

- 1) A small amount of the sample (subsample) is poured into a glass Petri dish
- 2) All subsamples are then visually examined and sorted under a stereomicroscope Olympus SZX7, 8x-56x) with attached digital camera (Nikon, DSL3)

Figure 16. Olympus SZX7, 8x-56x stereomicroscope with attached Nikon, DSL3 digital camera

3) When finding each MP item, it is manually separated using tweezers and then categorized according to physical properties (size, shape, color)

- **Size:** Table 7 describes the criteria used during this study to classify the plastic items found

Table 7. Size ranges of marine plastic litter.

Terminology	Size range
i. Macroplastics	>2.5 cm
ii. Mesoplastics	0.5 – ≤ 2.5 cm
iii. Large microplastics	1 – ≤5 mm
iv. Small microplastics	1 μm – ≤ 1000 μm
v. Nano plastics	1 nm – ≤ 1 μm

- **Shape:** Figure 17 illustrates the most common MPs shapes.

Figure 17. Shapes of typical microplastics collected from sea water (A: sheet; B: film; C: fiber; D: fragment; E: pellet/granule; F: foam)

- **Color:** The most common colors identified are: black, red, green, blue, white and transparent. The difference between white and transparent is the opacity, white is opaque and transparent is translucent. Colors such as purple, pink, grey, yellow or brown should be included in the category “Others”.

4) Separated MP items are dried and stored on a rectangular glass plate for later identification of polymer composition which is explained in part II.3.1.2.

Figure 18. Separated MP items dried and stored on a glass plate

II.3.1. Chemical identification of isolated microplastic items

Identification of polymer type can be done through various techniques. Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy coupled with Attenuated Total Reflection accessory (ATR-FTIR) and Micro-Raman spectroscopy (μ -RAMAN) are the most common techniques used for polymer identification. As the size of the plastic item decreases, the uncertainty of pure visual identification increases and the cost of the equipment needed for its analysis increases. Therefore, when selecting the appropriate analytical platform, the first consideration should be given to the size of MPs to be studied. Raman spectroscopy uses sub-micron wavelength lasers as its light source and, as such, is capable of resolving particles down to 1 μm and less. FTIR microscopy uses mid-infrared light as its source, resulting in a wavelength range that loses the ability to identify particles much below 100 μm . ATR-FTIR and μ -Raman spectroscopy are fundamental in MP studies for the confirmation of the chemical composition of items isolated from environmental samples. Without these analyses, plastic abundance may be strongly overestimated.

In this study we will focus on the characterization of MPs using FTIR spectrometer coupled with an ATR accessory. The principle behind this instrument is the interaction between light and matter (figure 19). A light source emits IR radiations at various frequencies, when these IR radiations hit the molecule, and if the applied IR frequency is equal to the natural frequency of vibration, absorption of IR radiation takes place. If not, the light transmits through the sample, the transmitted light is detected by the detector which is present inside the spectrometer, and based on that a spectrum is generated.

Figure 19. Infrared spectroscopy principle

In this study, a PerkinElmer Spectrum Two FTIR spectrometer equipped with ATR accessory with a 9-bounce diamond top-plate was used (Wave number range: 4000 cm⁻¹, 450 cm⁻¹) (figure 20). A computer was connected to the spectrometer to display and print the spectrograms.

Figure 20. PerkinElmer Spectrum Two Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometry Spectrometer

Characterization of MP items using FTIR spectrometer is done as following [43]:

- 1) The crystal is cleaned and the tip is pinned (the tip clamps the sample on the crystal). This is done to ensure the minimum possible interference on the data.
- 2) The next step is then to take background reading. the tip is tightened and the process starts. This must be done after every spectrum is recorded. The reason for this is that the air in the room contains contaminants such as carbon dioxide and water that can possibly interfere with the sample's spectrum.
- 3) The sample is directly placed on the ATR top plate mounted in the sample beam of the spectrometer. The measurements were completed within 30 seconds and ATR spectrum was obtained.
- 4) After measurement, the spectrum is compared to reference spectra through libraries supplied by Perkin Elmer, with a >60% similarity threshold.

In this project, 909 MP items were characterized using the FTIR. Figure 21 shows the spectrum of one random plastic item.

Figure 21. Search results for one random plastic item, showing a good match to the polypropylene reference

The MP polymer type was determined by matching the characteristic peaks of recorded spectra with the reference spectra of known plastics. In this example, the red spectra represent the one of the isolated

MP item and the black spectrum is the reference spectra. As seen in the photo, the results show a match of 0.98 to the PP reference. Since a match of more than 0.6 is obtained, then a confirmation about the chemical composition is done.

II.3.2 Fish samples analysis

II.3.2.1 Samples preparation and density separation of potential MPs

In order to detect the presence of MPs in fish samples, the fishes are dissected and the gastrointestinal tract, liver or other tissues are removed. Each sample tissue is then placed on a glass Petri dish and dried overnight in oven at 50°C. The dried sample is then triturated using a mortar (figure 22, B), until a powder is obtained, the powder is then put in a graduated cylinder and 100 ml and hyper saline solution is added to the sample for density separation of MPs (figure 22, C).

Figure 22. Pictures showing the recovery of MPs from fish sample

The solution is stirred and decanted for 10 min. After this, a first aliquot of supernatant is collected (figure 22, D). The materials used for the collection of the supernatant are also washed in order to collect particles potentially attached to the wall of glass tube and cylinder. This resuspension step is carried out twice for a better extraction performance. The supernatant of each resuspension is then

collected in a glass beaker and filtered in the filtration apparatus (figure 22, E). The membranes with retained materials are transferred in a Petri dish with 15% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) solution and put in the oven at 50°C overnight for the partial digestion of organic matter (figure 22, F).

II.3.2.2 Characterization of MPs from biota samples

The Petri dishes containing the H₂O₂ solution and the membranes containing the extracted MPs are microscopically observed and analyzed in the exact same way as water samples. MPs are photographed, measured at their largest cross section and categorized according to size, shape, and polymer type as described in part II.3.1.

II.3.3 Contamination control measures

To prevent contamination throughout the analysis process, all the materials used for sample collection, including the nets, were accurately cleaned and rinsed before any tow.

During the laboratory procedures glassware was used and particular care was taken to prevent airborne contamination by performing sample analysis in a clean air flow cabinet and using a glass Petri dish placed at the side of the stereomicroscope as blank control.

Despite the adoption of contamination control procedures, fibers and paint were not considered due to the risk of external contamination.

II.4 Preliminary ecotoxicological tests

The goal of this part is to study the effects caused by micro-sized plastics in marine crustaceans. Crustaceans are primary consumers and the most abundant metazoans in the marine ecosystem and therefore, they are widely used as bio-indicators in determining ecosystem quality with respect to environmental contaminants [44].

To achieve this goal, we assessed ingestion effects of commercially available PE beads in the planktonic stages of brine shrimp, *Artemia sp.* Brine Shrimp are small shrimp that live in extremely salty water, will hatch within 24 hours, and become mature in about one week. They have short life cycle, high adaptability to wide salinity range of 5–250 g/L as well as to temperatures from 6 to 35°C. Furthermore, they have high fecundity, small body size, and adaptability to varied nutrient resources as it is a nonselective filter feeder. In addition, their ability to produce dormant eggs, known as cysts, has led to extensive use of *Artemia* in aquaculture. The cysts may be stored for long periods and hatched

on demand. Moreover, the low cost and simplicity in use, turn it to be a model organism used to test the toxicity of chemicals.

The life cycle of *Artemia* begins as cysts, then emerged embryos, nauplii, finally larvae and adult. In the following tests, the MP effects are tested on *Artemia* in their nauplii stage.

3 steps are followed to conduct the test: hatching of *Artemia* cysts, MPs suspension preparation, exposure of organisms to MPs.

- **Hatching of *Artemia* cysts**

Dehydrated spherical cysts of *Artemia sp* (averaged 250-350 μm) were purchased and used for the experiments.

Figure 23. Figures showing the *Artemia* cysts and the *Artemia* organisms after hatching

The nauplii of the *Artemia sp.* were hatched by incubating the cysts for 24 h at 28 °C under light source and continuous aeration of the cyst suspension in seawater (37% salinity). The hatched organisms were transferred with a pipette into a beaker containing 0.22 μm filtered sea water (FSW).

- **Microplastics suspension preparation**

Two sizes of PE MPs were tested. In the first test, 1-4 μm fluorescent PE MPs were used (figure 24). In the second test, 20-25 μm PE MPs are tested.

Figure 24. Fluorescent PE MP used for the ecotoxicological test

MPs were sonicated for 1 min using a bath sonicator and then suspended in 0.22 μm filtered natural seawater up to 100 mg/L concentration. This stock concentration was used to bring MPs to the various concentrations used in the tests (0.001–0.01–0.1–1–10 mg/L). The tests were performed immediately after MPs suspension preparation.

- **Exposure of organisms to MPs**

10 organisms were transferred from the beaker into each well of a multi-well plates containing 1 mL of different MP concentrations (figure 25). They were incubated in the dark, for 24 and 48 h, at 25°C [45]. Controls using only seawater without MPs are run simultaneously.

Figure 25. Multi-well plates used in the ecotoxicological test

After exposure, mortality analysis was performed under a stereomicroscope: completely motionless organisms were counted as dead organisms, and the percentage of mortality was compared to the controls. Organisms that do not change their own barycenter position and do not move their appendages in 5 seconds are referred to as 'motionless' or 'not moving'. Mortality was evaluated in order to see whether such MPs rates may have toxic effects on the selected crustacean species.

Representative microscopy images for the organisms that digested MPs were taken using the biological fluorescence microscope BX41 (figure 26). Fluorescence microscopes use a light source to excite the fluorescent tags within a sample. In our case, we need to excite the fluorescent PE beads inside the artemia organisms. This is done in order to see if those organisms ate and digested the PE MPs or not.

Figure 26. Biological System Microscope BX41

The key concept behind this instrument is fluorescence. When a photon of light at a specific wavelength is absorbed by a molecule, an orbital electron jumps from its ground state to an excited state. As the electron returns to its ground state, it releases energy in the form of fluorescence (figure 27).

Figure 27. Fluorescence microscope principle

CHAPTER III - RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

III.1 Quality control

During sampling and sample handling, it is important to identify potential sources of plastic contamination. And for that purpose, a blank was checked continuously in the laboratory during the sample handling.

As seen in figure 28, fibers of different colors, mainly black and blue, were identified in the quality control and consequently, these items were excluded from the total count of detected MPs.

Figure 28. Examples of fibers found on the procedural blank during the analysis of water and fish samples: (A) black fiber, (B) and (C) blue fibers. (Red bar equals to 1 mm)

The main origin of these fibers is associated with airborne contamination, such as synthetic fibers stemming from clothing. For mitigating these contaminating risks, the sources of contamination should be eliminated and/or substantially reduced by wearing polymer-free clothing or cotton coveralls and gloves for example [47].

According to textile context, synthetic and regenerated materials are both manmade fibers, but of different origins. Apart from natural fibers, which are those found directly in nature, manmade are characterized by human interference in material formation [47] (Figure 29). Regenerated fibers are manufactured from plant-derived cellulose. Rayon and viscose are two of the most popular regenerated fibers. On the other hand, synthetic fibers can be generated by the synthesis of mainly petroleum substances. Thus, only synthetic textiles could be considered plastic.

Figure 29. Classification of textile fibers

Polyester and acrylic fibers dominate the textile market and account for almost 60% of the fibers used in the textile industry. Many steps should be taken in order to prevent the release of those fibers into the seas and oceans. For example, an important step to start with is upgrading the conventional wastewater treatment facilities by adding filters that catches microfibers.

III.2 MPs concentrations in sea surface water

For ease of comparability with other studies, the plastic concentrations in this study are expressed as plastic abundance per unit volume (items/m³). A high number of fibers was found in all samples, but these items were not included in the final estimates of plastics abundance since samples were likely to have been contaminated during onboard and laboratorial procedures.

The abundance of MPs at the 6 stations in the Gulf of Gabes is illustrated in figure 30. MPs are present 100% of the stations analyzed, suggesting the pervasion of MPs pollution in the area. A total of 1162 counts of MPs were detected at the 6 stations. The concentration of MPs differs from one station to another. It ranged between 0.23 and 2.50 items/m³ with a mean value of 1.16 items/m³ ($\pm 0.83SD$).

Station	Station 4	Station 5	Station 7	Station 8	Station 16	Station 17
Abundance(items/m ³)	0.81	1.78	2.50	0.23	0.89	0.73

Figure 30. Abundance of plastic items at each sampling station

The relatively high MP abundance at **station 7** (2.5 item/m³) may be attributed to its geographic proximity to Gabes port. This result confirms that the shipping and fishing industries are potent sources for MPs pollution at sea and that the discharge of ship-generated waste has a substantial environmental impact.

Taking into account the content of ships' garbage (plastics for example), this type of waste might be a relevant source for reusing or recycling supporting the transition towards a circular economy.

A comparison between each 2 adjacent stations shows that:

- The MPs abundance in station 5 is higher than station 4 ($\Delta = 0.97$)
- The MPs abundance in station 7 is higher than station 8 ($\Delta = 2.2$)
- The MPs abundance in station 16 is close to that in station 17 ($\Delta = 0.16$)

A trend of increasing abundance with distance from the shore is evident (the MPs abundance is lower in stations close to the shore and higher in the stations that are far from the shore). This result can be explained by the environmental factors and mainly the tidal movements in this area.

The tides observed in Gulf of Gabes are among the highest in the Mediterranean Sea (up to 2 m in height) [48] and they can help with the transport of MP items from the shore to the sea which result in higher MP concentrations in farther stations.

III.2.1 The situation of the Gulf of Gabes compared with other Mediterranean regions

Various units for MPs abundance (e.g., items/m², items/m³, g/m², items/kg, etc.) have been utilized in previous studies. Inconsistency in the sampling approach and reporting unites makes it difficult to compare MPs measurements results. In table 8, we compare our results with other studies with similar sampling reporting units.

Table 8. Literature data on microplastics abundance in Mediterranean surface waters

Site	Mesh size (µm)	Abundance (Items/m ³)
North Western Mediterranean Sea: Gulf of Lion	200	0.23 [49]
North Western Mediterranean Sea: Ligurian Sea and Sardinian Sea	200	0.62 [50]
Central Western Mediterranean Sea: Sardinian Sea	500	0.15 [51]
South western Mediterranean Sea: Gulf of Gabes	330	1.16 (present study)
South Eastern Mediterranean Sea: Israeli surface water	333	7.68 [52]
Eastern Mediterranean : Lebanese coast	52	4.3 [53]
Eastern Mediterranean: Turkish Mediterranean Coast	200	0.7 [54]

Concentration in the surface waters (1.16 MPs/m³) were high compared to other Mediterranean regions and particularly the Western part where MPs concentrations vary between 0.15 and 0.62 items/m³. This relatively high concentration of MPs compared to other Western Mediterranean regions is explained by the tidal effects present in the Gulf of Gabes.

In the Eastern Mediterranean, the MPs concentration fluctuates importantly across regions, ranging from 0.7 items/m³ in Northeast coast of Turkey to 7.68 items/m³ in the Israeli surface water. Although a small mesh size is used to collect MPs in Lebanon, a relatively high concentration is obtained which highlight the potential contribution of coastal landfills to this pollution.

Our result is relatively low compared to the Eastern Mediterranean regions. This result can be explained by many factors. First, the Eastern Mediterranean has been reported for its high contamination of floating plastic debris in comparison to the Western part. Differences between the two parts of the Mediterranean Sea is due to the different circulation patterns: water currents in the Western part promote circulation; whereas currents in the Eastern part are somewhat attractors leading to the accumulation of floating debris [56]. Another important factor is the different cultures in each part of the Mediterranean. Lack of awareness exist in the Eastern parts of the Mediterranean (Lebanon, Turkey, Israel) which lead to higher MPs concentrations in this part.

III.2.2 Abundance of MPs according to their shape

The MPs in the Gulf of Gabes has a broad range of shapes, including fragments, fibers, foams, pellets and films. Fragments (figure 31, A) were the most abundant particle shape found within the study area accounting for 96% of the total MPs found. Films (figure 31, B) were the second most abundant particle shape and contributed 3% of the total plastic count. The abundance of fibers (figure 31, C) never exceed more than 1% of the total composition. Sometimes we saw few foam shaped and pellets shapes like the ones in figure 17.

Figure 31. Pictures showing the shapes of microplastic debris detected: (A) yellow fragment, (B) transparent film, (C) black fiber. (Red bar equals to 1 mm)

Figure 32 illustrates the distribution of MP items by shape in each sampling station. Overall, there is evidence of a predominance of secondary MPs (fragments) making up 96% of the total particles

number. In total, 1162 MP items have been recorded within this study and 1131 of them were fragments and this suggests that the main driver of MPs pollution in the study zone is from the degradation of larger plastics from terrestrial sources.

The high proportion of MP fragments over other shapes of MPs is consistent with those in previous studies of plastic debris in surface seawater [57]. The fragments have various surface features, such as sharp edges with cracks or rounded shapes with smooth surfaces. Although we couldn't identify the sources of the fragments, their appearance may relate to their origin or history of degradation in the environment (sharp edges might indicate either recent introduction into the sea or the recent break-up of larger pieces, while smooth edges are often associated with older fragments that have been continuously polished by other particles or sediment [58])

Figure 32. Distribution of plastic items by shape at each sampling station

III.2.3 Size class distribution of MPs

Different sizes of MPs were detected. In order to better quantify the amount of micro sized plastic items, which are the center of this study, the items were divided into 3 size classes:

- Mesoplastics: > 5 mm
- Large microplastics: 1- 5 mm
- Small microplastics: < 1 mm

The diagram below shows the distribution of each size class in the stations. Our analysis results show that the size of 72% of the detected MPs spans from 1 to 5 mm. 27% of MPs are small size (<1mm), while 0.86% of MPs are macro sized. Meso sized plastics were the least dominant in all stations and they never exceed 2% of the total count.

Figure 33. Distribution of plastic items according to their size

In addition, the MPs (large and small) were the most dominant class size in all the stations thus confirming that MPs as the most abundant type of marine debris in sea water [59]. Since the smallest particles are most abundant here, it is probable that these MPs are in their early stage of fragmentation.

This result also confirms that the fragmentation of larger plastic items into smaller ones is the main driver of MP pollution. We can also note that the percentage of the small MPs (<1 mm) increase with distance from shore which is explained by the fact that smaller particles can be transported for longer distances compared to bigger particles (1 to 5 mm).

The mesh size of the net can influence the size distribution as well as the speed of the tow, as smaller particles avoiding the net can be forced aside from the net opening or large particles can squeeze out through the mesh. This study used a 330 μm mesh sized net.

III.2.4 Polymers characterization of MPs

PE was found to be the most abundant (73%) plastic type among the identified MP items in the research area. Other identified polymers include PP (10%) and Ethylene-vinyl acetate EVA (7%). The proportion of the polymers found in our study roughly corresponds to the global production stocks of plastic materials, with polyolefins (PE and PP) accounting for 62% of the global plastic demand and for 83% of our sampled items.

Figure 34. Distribution of MPs according to their chemical composition

PE and PP are the two predominant plastic polymers in our MPs samples, consistent with earlier findings [60]. Being widely used in the disposable packaging industry and having lower densities than seawater, it is not surprising that these polymers consistently account for the majority of the plastic particles floating in surface waters worldwide. PE is the most common plastic on a global scale and consequently the most dominant plastic debris in the Mediterranean Sea and worldwide, deriving mainly from plastic bags and bottles.

Further studies should be done in order to know and to locate the types of industries in the area, the types of effluent and the types of landfills. Those informations are strongly needed for a better interpretation of the results.

A total number of 909 items were examined with ATR-FTIR spectroscopy. 850 items of them were assessed to be plastic polymers, 57 particles were assessed to be “non plastic” which means that 6.27% of the analyzed items did not consist of plastic but were rather made of viscose, wax, cellulose and other non-synthetic materials (table 9). This reveal a relatively low misidentification rate during visual sorting. The distribution of the non-plastic items is shown in the table below.

Table 9. Non plastic items found in the analyzed samples

Type	viscose	inorganic	cellulose	resin	wax
Number of items	31	21	3	1	1

III.3 MPs in fish samples

Plastic items were detected in 5% of the examined fish samples. 10 *PE* species were examined and we found that they had not ingested any plastic items. One the other hand, plastic was found in one out of 10 *SS* species.

Figure 35. The plastic item found in the digestive tract of one specimen of *Scomber scombrus* (Red bar equals 1 mm)

The MP item found is a blue fragment having a size of 0.13 mm. The chemical composition of this item is not confirmed because it is too small and thus we need to characterize it using Micro-Raman spectroscopy which is not available in the laboratory. In our study, most MPs isolated in fishes were fibers, which we exclude to derive from secondary pollution (fibers from clothes, contamination from the air, etc.). When working on MPs, fiber contamination of samples is a potential problem that needs to be addressed by specific protocols.

III.4 Preliminary ecotoxicological results

III.4.1 The effects of 1-4 μm fluorescent PE MPs on *Artemia sp.* nauplii

Microscopy observations showed that fluorescent PE MPs (1-4 μm) were ingested within 24h and 48h, and were accumulated in the gut of the crustaceans. Toxicity tests results with nauplii of the *Artemia sp.* exposed to different MPs concentrations are reported in table 10 and figure 36.

Figure 36. Representative microscopy images of *Artemia sp.* nauplii revealing MPs inside the invertebrates after 48 h of the control and with exposure to 0.01 and 1 mg/L.

Table 10. Percentage of mortality and immobilization observed in nauplii exposed to 1-4 μm fluorescent PE MPs

After $t = 24$ hours						
Concentration (mg/L)	0 (controls)	0.001	0.01	0.1	1	10
%mortality	1.85	1.39	4.44	0	4.98	2.78
%immobilization	1.85	1.39	6.67	1.96	4.98	2.78
After $t = 48$ hours						
Concentration (mg/L)	0 (controls)	0.001	0.01	0.1	1	10
%mortality	4.44	0	4.44	3.06	2.90	0
%immobilization	4.44	1.39	6.67	4.72	4.57	0

Mortality and immobilization were affected by PE MP in *Artemia sp.* nauplii, and after 24h and 48h of exposure, they were both impaired mainly by 0.01 and 1 mg/L concentration of MP, where a difference was observed between exposed nauplii and controls. No difference was found at the other

concentrations. The highest mortality was observed at a concentration of 1 mg/L and it equals 4.98% which is considered as tolerable effect (<10%). This result may be due to the fact that the organisms will take out the MPs after ingestion. A continuous exposure to MPs is needed in order to accumulate MPs inside the guts of the organisms and thus to see higher effects.

As shown in figure 37, the organisms did not ingest MP in a dose-dependent manner and despite high MP concentrations used in this study (> 1 mg/L), limited mortality was observed in brine shrimps after 2 days. The concentration of 10 mg/L didn't result in the highest effects. These findings suggest that at higher concentrations, MPs tend to aggregate which means that it will be impossible for the organisms to eat it because of its large size.

Figure 37. Percentage of mortality and immobilization of *Artemia nauplii* after 24 and 48 h of exposure to increasing concentrations of 1-4 µm fluorescent PE MPs

In addition, the effects observed after 24h are higher than those observed after 48h of the test. An exception is seen at a concentration of 0.1 mg/L where the mortality and immobilization highly rise after 48h. This indicates that higher exposure time didn't necessarily result in higher effects and this may be due to the aggregation of MPs after longer time. The experimental setup and exposure time are two parameters that should be further taken into account for MP toxicity assessment.

III.4.2 The effects of 20-25 µm polyethylene MPs on *Artemia sp. nauplii*

In the second test where larger MPs particles (20-25 µm) were used, we could not see any effects after 24 hours (table 11, figure 38) which demonstrates that bigger MP particles aggregate faster and after 24h of the test, the MPs were already aggregated so they didn't cause any effects to the organisms.

Another explanation is that bigger MPs particles need more time to be ingested by the organisms and thus longer time to affect the mortality and immobilization.

Table 11. Percentage of mortality and immobilization of Artemia sp. nauplii exposed to 20-25 μm PE MPs

<i>After t=24 hours</i>					
Concentration (mg/L)	0 (controls)	0.01	0.1	1	10
%mortality	0	0	0	0	0
%immobilization	0	0	0	0	0
<i>After t=48 hours</i>					
Concentration (mg/L)	0 (controls)	0.01	0.1	1	10
%mortality	2.86	2.86	0.72	5.79	1.52
%immobilization	9.11	4.71	0.72	6.71	1.52

Figure 38. Percentage of mortality and immobilization of Artemia sp. nauplii after 24 and 48 h of exposure to increasing concentrations of 20-25 μm PE MPs

After 48h of the test, we can see that there were little effects with all the concentrations used but these effects are still considerable tolerable (<10%). The highest mortality and immobilization were observed at a concentration of 1 mg/L consistent with the previous test. Overall, we can say that a concentration of 1 mg/L will cause relatively higher effects compared to other concentrations. Repetition of the tests with longer exposure time and continuous MPs exposure are needed to obtain powerful results.

III.4.2 Comparison between the effects caused by 1-4 and 20-25 µm MPs

The chart below compare the effects of the MPs size on the mortality and immobilization. After 48h of exposure, and at lower concentrations, the smaller MP items result in higher effects on both the mortality and the immobilization of the organisms. However, with higher concentrations (>1 mg/L), the bigger MP items caused more effects. This suggest that, for the moment, no correlation exists between the size of the MP items and the effects caused by its ingestion.

Figure 39. Percentage of mortality and immobilization of *Artemia sp. nauplii* after 48 h of exposure to 1-4 µm and 20-25 µm PE MPs

The results obtained with ecotoxicological tests are preliminary results and in order to confirm them, the tests must be repeated for at least 3 times. We also suggest the use of bigger MPs (1 to 5 mm) which are the most abundant MP size in water samples that we analyzed.

CONCLUSION AND PROSPECTS

The ubiquity of MPs in the marine environment has been previously reported. This is the first study in the Gulf of Gabes presenting an integrated picture of MPs pollution.

Our results show that the study area is contaminated by MPs in all studied compartments. MPs have been found in 100% of the seawater samples, with an average abundance of $1.16 \text{ items/m}^3 \pm 0.83 \text{ SD}$. Dominance in number of fragments over other shapes of MPs was reported in all sites. 73% of the items analyzed consist of polyethylene. MPs were also found in 5% of the biota samples. We suggest that, in future work, other types of fishes should be analyzed.

Plastic fibers have been observed in both water and fish samples. Plastic fiber presence could be due to air-borne contamination during sampling procedures. Therefore, when working on MPs, a careful data interpretation as well as standardized methods during sampling and lab activities are mandatory; standardization of methodologies for identification and quantification of MPs in the marine environment and formulation of standard operating procedures is strongly needed.

In addition to water and fish samples, we also suggest the analysis of sediments samples from Gabes beach for a better understanding of the presence of MPs in the area.

We demonstrated that polyethylene microbeads which accumulate in the nauplii of the brine shrimp, only affect sub-lethal responses at environmental and high MP concentrations. We propose that, in the future, other sub-lethal parameters such as swimming activity should be considered as a suitable tool for detecting high MP contamination level. We also propose to test other polymers such as PP and PS.

Irrespective of different polymers sources and typologies, the problem of plastic pollution is a social and behavioral issue, whose causes require to be mostly sought upstream in the consumption chain. There is no miracle solution! Genuine solutions will arise from collective action by civil society, policymakers and business. If just one of these groups doesn't fulfill its role in the tri-party scenario, the solutions will fail.

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